

Sol-gel method of synthesis and characterization of some mixed-oxide nanocomposites

Geetika Borah^{a*}, Pradip K. Gogoi^a, Aicharjya Borah^a and Ponchami Sharma^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Dibrugarh University, Dibrugarh-786 004, Assam, India

E-mail : geetikachem@yahoo.co.in

^bCoal Chemistry Division, NEIST, Jorhat-785 006, Assam, India

Manuscript received 6 October 2009, accepted 31 May 2010

Abstract : Nanosized crystallites of the mixed oxides BaCuO₂ (1), BaNiO₂ (2), Ba₂Co₄O_{7.8} (3) and Ba₂CuCe₂O₇ (4) were synthesized by comparatively inexpensive route : Sol-Gel method. The particle size and morphology were studied by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). The crystallinity, average crystalline size and phase purity of the prepared nanocomposites were analyzed by powder X-ray diffraction technique (XRD). The results indicated that all the samples had good crystallinity and composed of multiple phases with the exception of BaNiO₂. The average crystalline sizes were found to be in the range 29-44 nm. Impedance measurements in the temperature range 303-363 K reveal decrease of bulk resistance (R_b) with increase of temperature upto 333 K, indicating semiconducting behaviour in this temperature range. The energy gap (E_g) measurements via Four-Probe setup instrument reveal that they fall in the range 0.15-2.15 eV.

Keywords : Sol-gel method, X-ray method, electron microscopy, impedance, Four-Probe method.

Introduction

Nanostructured metals and ceramics have improved mechanical properties compared to bulk materials and seem to be good candidates for near catalytic applications^{1,2}. Mixed metal oxides, containing Cu, Co, Fe, Ni etc. have been found as selective catalyst of NH₃ oxidation and their activity strongly depend on the kind of transition metal introduced to the mixed oxides system. The highest activity was observed for the copper containing catalysts³. Copper oxide (CuO) is a semiconducting compound with a monoclinic structure. CuO has attracted particular attention because it is the simplest member of the family of copper compounds and exhibits a range of potentially useful physical properties such as high temperature superconductivity, electron correlation effects and spin dynamics^{4,5}. As an important p-type semiconductor, CuO has found many diverse applications such as in gas sensors, catalysis, batteries, solar energy conversion and field emission emitters. In the energy-saving area, energy transferring fluids filled with nano CuO particles can improve fluid viscosity and enhance thermal conductivity⁶. CuO crystal structures possess a narrow band gap, giving useful photocatalytic as well as photo-

conductive functionalities⁷. CuO nanoparticles were also effective in killing a range of bacterial pathogens involved in hospital-acquired infections⁸. Nickel and cobalt oxides have applications as electrochemical capacitors and in coloured glasses. Nanoclusters of cobalt oxide have been used as catalyst in the oxidation of cyclohexane⁹. Co, Ba, K/CeO₂ solid is an efficient trap of NO_x and at the same time, an active catalyst for soot combustion¹⁰. After investigating various oxide fine particles^{11,12}, it was observed that with the reduction in size to nanoscale, the lattice of oxide material tends to acquire higher structural symmetry resulting in altogether new properties due to structure property co-relationship. Therefore, research is focused on the synthesis and characterization of high-tech multimetal oxides as nanoparticles or thin films. Aqueous solution synthesis methods are preferred for several reasons, among which economical and ecological advantages, the flexibility to tailor the end product are most notable. Recently, more attention is being paid to a water based solution gel route that involves the formation of a gel network by hydrolysis, condensation and complexation reactions in an aqueous solution of metal salts and chelating ligands. A subsequent heat treatment transforms

the amorphous gel into the desired nanosized metal oxide. Very often the gel components behave as fuel for autocombustion to provide extra heat energy.

In the present investigation we report the preparation of ultrafine mixed oxides of compositions BaCuO_2 , BaNiO_2 , $\text{Ba}_2\text{Co}_4\text{O}_{7.8}$ and $\text{Ba}_2\text{CuCe}_2\text{O}_7$ using well proved sol-gel technique, which produce fine particles of narrow size distribution and controlled chemical composition at comparably lower temperature range. These nano oxides might have improved mechanical, electrical as well as catalytic applications. These materials have been characterized by SEM and XRD techniques. Electrical properties have been investigated with the help of impedance and band gap measurements.

Experimental

Materials :

The salts $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, $\text{BaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ used in this study were of LR grade (Rankem or BDH) and $\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was from Loba Chemie. Citric acid, which was used as gel forming agent as well as fuel for autocombustion was of IP grade (Rankem). Methanol and glycerol used were of LR grade (Rankem). All the solvents were distilled before use.

Physical measurements :

The grain size and morphology were measured by using scanning electron microscope (SEM model LEICA S430). X-Ray diffraction pattern were recorded by using Bruker AXS X-ray diffractometer (model : D8 Advance) using $\text{CuK}_{\alpha 1}$ radiation with 2θ ranges from 10 – 80° . SEM photographs and XRD were obtained from IIT, Guwahati. The average crystallite size, d was measured from the XRD based on Scherrer's equation :

$$d = 0.89\lambda / \beta \cos \theta \quad (1)$$

where, λ is the wavelength of the X-rays, θ is the diffraction angle and β is the full width at half maximum.

Impedance measurements in the temperature range 303 – 363 K were carried out on Impedance Analyser (model : HIOKI LCR HiTESTER 3522). Energy gap measurements in the temperature range 298 – 423 K by Four-Probe setup instrument (made by Scientific Instruments Company, Roorkee, India) were done in the Department of Physics, Dibrugarh University, Dibrugarh.

Synthesis of mixed-oxide nanocomposites :

These multimetal nanooxides were prepared by sol-gel

auto combustion technique by using citric acid as fuel.

Synthesis of BaCuO_2 (1) : The precursor aqueous solution was prepared by mixing solutions of $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ (50 ml, 0.02 M) and $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ (50 ml, 0.1 M) with 8 ml methanol and citric acid (100 ml, 0.40 M) followed by slow evaporation (kept for 6 days at room temperature) of the solution to form amorphous gel and subsequently pyrolysed at 1073 K for 13 h to obtain fine powder.

Synthesis of BaNiO_2 (2) : The precursor aqueous solution was prepared by adding stoichiometric amount of $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ (50 ml, 0.02 M) and $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ (50 ml, 0.1 M) solutions with 8 ml methanol and citric acid (100 ml, 0.45 M), which was kept for 10 days at room temperature for slow evaporation and gel formation and was subsequently pyrolysed at 1073 K for 17 h to get nanooxide.

Synthesis of $\text{Ba}_2\text{Co}_4\text{O}_{7.8}$ (3) : An equimolar solution mixture of BaCl_2 and CoCl_2 was prepared by adding 30 ml, 0.07 M of each solution and to it 5 ml methanol and citric acid (9 ml, 0.43 M) were added. The precursor solution was heated slowly, kept for 5 days at room temperature for evaporation and gel formation. The gel was pyrolysed at 1073 K for 16 h to form fine oxide.

Synthesis of $\text{Ba}_2\text{CuCe}_2\text{O}_7$ (4) : The precursor aqueous solution was prepared by mixing solutions of BaCl_2 (50 ml, 1 M), $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ (50 ml, 1 M), $\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ (50 ml, 0.42 M) with glycerol (18 ml) and citric acid (150 ml, 5 M), followed by slow evaporation (kept for 12 days at room temperature) and was burned at 1373 K for 21 h to obtain fine oxide.

Results and discussion

SEM micrographs (Figs. 1 and 2) reveal that there is lack of uniformity in shapes and sizes of the particles and consist of grains with typical dimensions 32 – 59 nm (Table 1). The average crystallite sizes estimated from

Fig. 1. SEM of BaCuO_2 .

Fig. 2. SEM of Ba₂CuCe₂O₇.

Table 1. Particle size, avg. crystalline size and phases present

Sample code	Particle size ^a (nm)	Avg. crystalline size (nm) (2θ) ^c	Phases present
BaCuO ₂	32.4–47.7	29.1 (39°)	Cubic and monoclinic
BaNiO ₂	47.5–58.7	29.5 (43°)	Cubic
Ba ₂ Co ₄ O _{7,8}	43.5–53.6	43.4 (37°)	Cubic and hexagonal
Ba ₂ CuCe ₂ O ₇	52.8–58.5	42.4 (28.5°)	Cubic and monoclinic

^aFrom SEM and ^bfrom XRD.

^cXRD peak used to calculate avg. crystalline size.

the full width at half maximum intensity of the reflections : 111 (2θ = 39°), 200 (2θ = 43°), 220 (2θ = 37°), 111 (2θ = 28.5°) for BaCuO₂, BaNiO₂, Ba₂Co₄O_{7,8}, Ba₂CuCe₂O₇ respectively, fall in the range 29–44 nm. The observed *d*-lines pattern for BaCuO₂ was found to correspond cubic BaO¹³ [observed plane diffractions : (200), (311), (222), (400)] and monoclinic CuO¹⁴ [observed plane diffractions : (111), (111), (112), (202), (020), (113), (022)] phases, indicating the presence of multiple phases, while BaNiO₂ consists of BaO [observed plane diffractions : (111), (220), (222)] and NiO [observed plane diffractions : (111), (200)] each with cubic structure^{13,15}. The structure of Ba₂Co₄O_{7,8}, as identified by XRD can be indexed to the cubic BaO [observed plane diffractions : (111), (220), (311), (222)] and Co₃O₄ [observed plane diffractions : (111), (220), (311), (400), (511), (440)] and hexagonal BaCo₂O₈ [observed plane diffractions : (100), (101), (110), (002), (211)]^{13,16,17}. The XRD pattern of Ba₂CuCe₂O₇ also reveals the presence of multiple phases, where BaO [observed plane diffractions : (111), (220), (311), (222)], CeO₂ [observed plane diffractions : (111), (200), (220), (311), (400)] and BaCeO₃ [observed plane diffractions : (310)] crystallized with cubic and CuO [observed plane diffractions : (002), (020), (202), (113)] with monoclinic structure^{13,14,18,19}.

The XRD patterns of BaCuO₂ and Ba₂CuCe₂O₇ are given in Figs. 3 and 4 respectively.

Fig. 3. XRD pattern of BaCuO₂ nanocomposite.

Fig. 4. XRD pattern of Ba₂CuCe₂O₇ nanocomposite.

Impedance measurements in the temperature range 303–363 K (Table 2) reveal increase of conductance with temperature upto 333 K, indicating semiconducting nature within this temperature range, while beyond the range

Fig. 5. Complex impedance plots of $\text{Ba}_2\text{Co}_4\text{O}_{7.8}$ at temperatures 303–363 K : (a) 303, (b) 313, (c) 323, (d) 333, (e) 343, (f) 353 and (g) 363 K.

Table 2. The values of conductivity of the synthesized nano-composites at different temperatures

Sample code	Conductivity (σ)=(t/AR_p) (S cm ⁻¹)						
	303 K	313 K	323 K	333 K	343 K	353 K	363 K
1	9.81×10^{-8}	2.02×10^{-7}	2.09×10^{-7}	4.15×10^{-7}	5.98×10^{-7}	6.05×10^{-8}	8.04×10^{-8}
2	1.69×10^{-8}	5.12×10^{-8}	1.92×10^{-7}	4.83×10^{-7}	6.03×10^{-7}	3.76×10^{-8}	2.73×10^{-8}
3	1.55×10^{-7}	1.62×10^{-7}	1.68×10^{-7}	2.23×10^{-7}	1.98×10^{-7}	2.70×10^{-7}	2.37×10^{-7}
4	2.73×10^{-8}	3.52×10^{-8}	7.02×10^{-8}	8.67×10^{-8}	7.65×10^{-8}	6.91×10^{-8}	3.88×10^{-8}

t = thickness of the pellets, A is the surface area of the pellets = 1.3002495×10^{-2} cm².

this trend of conductivity was not observed. For good semiconductor the conductivity value falls within the range 10^{-5} – 10^{-2} S cm⁻¹ ²⁰. Figs. 5(a-g) show the complex impedance plot of Ba₂Co₄O_{7.8} at different temperatures. The energy gaps were found to fall in the range 0.15–2.2 eV for the generated oxides, while pure semiconductors show band gap in the range 0.5–3.0 eV²¹. Fig. 6 shows the plot of $\ln \rho$ vs $1/T$ for band gap calculation of BaNiO₂.

Fig. 6. $\ln \rho$ vs $1/T$ curve of BaNiO₂ nanocomposite for band gap calculation.

Conclusions :

It can be concluded that multimetal oxides of different compositions can be synthesized through sol-gel auto combustion techniques with citric acid as a fuel. The particle and average crystalline sizes of the generated oxides fall in the range 32–59 nm and 29–44 nm respectively, with lack of uniformity in shapes and sizes. The oxides were found to consist of multiple phases with the exception of BaNiO₂, which crystallized with cubic symmetry. Impedance and band gap analyses indicate their semiconducting behaviour within the temperature range 303–333 K.

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to thank CIF, IIT, Guwahati and Centre for Nanotechnology, IIT, Guwahati, for car-

rying out SEM photographs and XRD.

References

1. D. D. Beck and R. W. Seigel, *J. Mater. Res.*, 1992, 7, 2840.
2. E. Boakye, L. R. Radovic and K. Osseo-Asare, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 1994, 163, 120.
3. L. Chmielarz, P. Kustrowski, A. R. Lasocha and R. Dziembay, *Applied Catalysis B : Environmental*, 2005, 58, 235.
4. R. J. Cava, *Science*, 1990, 247, 656.
5. J. M. Tranquada, B. J. Sternlieb, J. D. Axe, Y. Nakamura and S. Uchida, *Nature*, 1995, 375, 561.
6. K. Kwak and C. Kim, *Korea-Australia Rheol J.*, 2005, 17, 35.
7. J. F. Xu, W. Ji, Z. X. Shen, S. H. Tang, X. R. Ye and D. Z. Jia, *J. Solid State Chem.*, 1999, 147, 516.
8. G. Ren, D. Hu, E. W. C. Cheng, M. A. Vargas-Reus, P. Reip and R. P. Allaker, *International Journal of Antimicrobial Agents*, 2009, 33, 589.
9. R. V. Narayan, V. Kanniah and A. Dhathathreyan, *J. Chem., Sci.*, 2006, 118, 179.
10. V. G. Milt, C. A. Querini, E. E. Miro and M. A. Ulla, *J. Catal.*, 2003, 220, 424.
11. P. Ayyub, "Nanomaterials", ed. D. Chakravorty, Indian National Science Academy, New Delhi, 2001, 71.
12. V. R. Palkar, P. Ayyub, S. Chattopadhyay and M. Multani, *Phys. Rev. (B)*, 1996, 53, 2167.
13. JCPDS 1-0746.
14. JCPDS 5-0661.
15. JCPDS 4-0835.
16. JCPDS 9-418.
17. JCPDS 10-245.
18. JCPDS 4-0593.
19. JCPDS 1-0803.
20. A. R. West, "Solid State Chemistry and its Applications", John Wiley & Sons (Asia) Pvt. Ltd., Singapore, 2005, Chap. 13, pp. 453-456.
21. A. R. West, "Solid State Chemistry and its Applications", John Wiley & Sons (Asia) Pvt. Ltd., Singapore, 2005, Chap. 14, pp. 510-515.

